
June, 2021

Nigeria Navigating Insurgence To Banditry And Avoidable Resurgence Mayday Approach

By

Dr AYoola Gabriel Ololade FCIA NIA

Ph.D. Pub Admin, Ph.D. H/Int. Studies

Administrative & Academic Consultant

[The Ideal Schools Ltd. \(TIS\)](#) | [Ambrose Alli University \(AAU\)](#)

- **Email:** dr_ayoola_gabriel@tis.ng
- **ORCID:** [0009-0000-9263-2854](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9263-2854)
- **SSRN Author ID:** [11717808](https://ssrn.com/author/11717808)
- **Linked In:** [linkedin.com/in/dr-gabriel-ayoola](https://www.linkedin.com/in/dr-gabriel-ayoola)
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.20450427](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20450427)

Ayoola Oseyemi O MSc (Public Administration AAU)

Icheme Monday Ojochide. PhD (Department of Management Science, University of Nigeria (UNN)
Enugu State, Nigeria)

Olasupo A Solomon PhD (Peace Security and Strategic Studies, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria)

Akinrinade. S. Adewuyi PhD (Political Science, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria)

ABSTRACT: The transformation of Boko Haram Islamic fundamentalist sect to a terrorist group since 2009 has created a state of palpable fear in the northern part of Nigeria, while the general impression that government is incapable of arresting the tides and the ripples generated have led to social, economic, political, and security challenges in Nigeria. The scenario informed this study to examine the growth of the sect, the efforts of government in addressing the issues as well as the lesson from the insurgence. The study was primarily descriptive while data were obtained from secondary sources. The study found that the prolonged insurgence was a manifestation of high level of frustration on account of poverty and unemployment while the institutional mechanism adopted in managing the crisis through security approach to peace was defective. The study concludes that the challenges are not insurmountable while it is a reflection of a weak state. The study therefore recommends that the government should adopt a proactive security measures directed at preventing rather than resolving direct violence. In addition, government should adopt peace approach to security and engage in programmes and policies that will judiciously and equitably address poverty and unemployment. Lastly, the southern states should review their agriculture policies to encourage the production of vegetables and crops that could be grown all year round without irrigation as this will reduce over-dependence on northern sources particularly in periods of crises, disaster or crop failure.

Keywords: Boko Haram, Banditry, Muslims, Herdsmen, Kidnappers, Human Security Christians, Cleavages, and Northern Nigeria.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terrorism is largely becoming a household word globally as there is no nation that is completely absolved from the effect. Globalization has significantly influenced the space of terrorism as the event in

one part of the globe has direct or an indirect effect on others. This explains why Horne (2002) in Rourke (2008) observes that war, terrorism and other forms of transnational political violence are in many ways more threatening today than ever before as civilian casualty has been on increase globally. It is however difficult to evolve a single definition for the term “terrorism”. The difficulty emanated from lack of consensus or unified perspective among nations or scholars as what could be regarded as terrorist act.

Kydd & Walter (2006) define terrorism as actions focusing on harming some people in order to create fear in others by targeting civilians and facilities or system on which civilians rely. However, the scope of the operation of the Boko Haram sect has gone beyond civilian targets including the UN building, Police Headquarters and Military establishment. This paper acknowledges that discussions on the subject matter may be subjective since it is a function of individual's perceptions. However, for the purpose of this study, terrorism is viewed as violence perpetrated by individuals within or outside the government that is specifically directed against civilian or government institution as a way of calling attention to perceived real or imaginary injustices in a clandestine manner. This definition largely captures the modus operandi of the Boko Haram that one could conveniently refer to it as a domestic terrorist organization.

Banditry means occurrence or prevalence of armed robbery or violent crime. It involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person with the intent to rob, rape or kill. Banditry is a crime against persons. It has been a common genre of crime, as well as cause violence in contemporary societies, Nigeria Watch, (2011). Rural banditry associated with cattle rustling has become a major concern for public policy in contemporary Nigeria. It refers to the practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders, or the raiding of cattle from the ranches. Although driven by different needs and factors, it is increasingly an economically-based form of criminality perpetuated by informal networks (Kwaja, 2013). Rural banditry thrives as a means of 'primitive' accumulation of cowherds in the context of subsistence and commercial pastoralism. The most disturbing effect of this banditry is the unsettling of pastoralist transhumant activities. Furthermore, rural banditry is accompanied by rape, kidnapping, organized attacks on villages and communities, and looting. While in essence human security entails how an aspect of human lives will be protected which mainly includes personal security, community security, political security, food security, health security, educational security, environmental security and what have you UNDP (1994). A "more explicit definition" of human security is provided by two main aspects: "safety from such chronic threats as hunger, disease and repression," and "protection from sudden and hurtful disruption in the patterns of daily life." Quoting the US Secretary of State reporting to his government on the results of conference in San Francisco in 1945 that set up the United Nations, the Report emphasized that the two freedoms, "freedom from fear" and "freedom from want," were recognized at the founding of the UN. The Report deplures, however, that the concept of security has been linked only to "freedom from fear UNDP (1994).

The main thrust of this study is to determine the Nigeria navigating insurgence to banditry and avoidable resurgence mayday approach to achieve this, therefore, the following objectives as it points: to determine the new trends to insurgency groups in Nigeria, to ascertain the remote and immediate causes of Boko Haram crisis in Nigeria, to ascertain the socio-Political and religious implication of Boko Haram crisis in Nigeria, to determine the impacts of the insurgency group activities on Nigeria foreign policy and to determine how the Nigeria citizens can serve as a helping hand in tackling the Boko Haram crisis in Nigeria.

The research is divided into five sections. The first is the introductory part, background of the study, statement of the problem, followed by conceptual clarifications. The third section examines the literature review and theoretical framework. The fourth section examines origin of terrorism (Boko Haram) in Nigeria, Causes of Kidnapping, Banditry, Hostage Taking and Insurgency in Nigeria and Implication of Boko Haram insurgency on Nigeria foreign policy. The final section is the conclusion and recommendations.

This study adopts the qualitative research method of the social sciences was adopted; this method includes gathering data from several sources, e.g. books, texts, the internet, journals and other source that form the body of scholarly works on the subject matter has been used in this study. The techniques for

analyzing these secondary data are textual analysis and explanatory method. Textual analysis implies analyzing the content of books, journal articles, monographs, unpublished theses and internet materials. Explanatory method implies interpretation of existing texts on a subject matter. It means drawing inferences, premises, conclusions and implications from a scholar's work. This explanatory method is germane to the study of rural banditry given the importance of interpretation to this work.

Background to the Study

The phenomenon of militants is not new to Nigeria. The history of post-independent Nigeria is replete with cases of militarized groups threatening the very existence of the Nigerian state. But of all the militant groups that have sprung up in Nigeria, the Boko Haram remains the most enigmatic in terms of *raison d'être*, the most violent in terms of *modus operandi* and the most destructive. It is arguably second to none in terms of brutality, savagery, wanton destruction, callousness, in its scope of operation. Since the Civil War of 1967–1970, the group has presented the most frontal attack on the Nigerian state as a corporate entity, particularly concerning the long march toward the unity and peaceful coexistence of its disparate nationalities. And quite unlike its precursors, who had clear-cut demands, a base, and a driving philosophy, Boko Haram has been described as a group with “no headquarters, no known place of doing business, no central leadership or authority; working, instead, as a decentralized franchise operation.” With shifting objectives and a virulent operation, the group has been operating with impunity, leaving in its trail, blood, death, wailing, and destruction.

In 2011, the group carried out 136 attacks that resulted in the death of 559 people. In 2012, the insurgency caused the death of over a thousand people, cutting across ethnic groups, religions, and regions, the single biggest being Kano, where about 185 people were killed in one day. On April 16, 2013, an estimated number of 37 people were reportedly killed in a single operation in Baga community. In May 2013, the terrorists attacked Bama military barracks, killed 50 people, and freed 105 inmates from the prison. On July 12, 2013, students were massacred in a secondary school in Damaturu. This was followed by another 33 students two weeks later in Mamudo, Yobe state. On September 17, 2013, about 161 people were reported killed during an attack on civilians at Benisheik border town in Borno state. A few days later, September 29, 2013, about 42 students of the School of Agriculture, Gujba, Yobe State, were massacred during a night raid. On December 2, 2013, Boko Haram operatives staged daring attacks on airforce formations and police stations in Maiduguri, killed scores of people, and set fighter jets and buildings ablaze. On December 20, 2013, Boko Haram terrorists staged a raid on a military barracks in Bama and left scores of people dead. On January 23, 2014, Boko Haram's operations in Waga Chakawa town in Adamawa killed 30 people, mostly worshippers in a Catholic church. In another operation on the same day in Kawuri village in Borno State, Boko Haram terrorists staged an invasion in 26 vehicles, two armoured personnel carrier and 6 pickup trucks. At the end of the bloody operation, 85 people were dead and 7 mosques and 300 houses burned.

Many insightful analyses have emerged to explain the genesis and *raison d'être* of Boko Haram. Freedom Onuoha, Nathaniel Danjibo, Abimbola Adesoji, Peter Pham, Roland Marchal, and Babjee Pothuraju see the phenomenon as a manifestation of religious fervors built on fundamentalist indoctrination that is traceable to the era of the 1980s Maitatsine uprising in Kano and as well to being influenced by contemporary global jihadist utopianism of Al Qaeda and its affiliates Al-Shabab of Somalia, Taliban of Afghanistan, and Al Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM). In the analysis of Kwesi Aning, the group's emergence is not to be found in ideological radicalism alone but rather on the failure of governance in Nigeria. Boko Haram, therefore, is a manifestation of pervasive decadence in the upper echelon of leadership in Nigeria, as evident in unbridled corruption, pervasive inefficiency, and general impunity. Hakeem Onapajo, Ufo Okeke-Uzodike, and Ayo Whetho explore the international dimension of Boko Haram and pro-vide clear evidence that, to a large extent, the philosophy, operational tactics,

funding, and inspirational drivers of Boko Haram are located beyond the shores of Nigeria. This international dimension was also reflected in Akin Oyebo's statement that Boko Haram is essential "a local tentacle of a global octopus." However, to David Cook, Jonathan Hill, and Valerie Thompson, the whole discourse of Boko Haram should be situated within the context of tension between the Sufi and Salafist doctrines. While Sufism centres on an esoteric interpretation of Islam, focusing on the soul as against social action, Salafism gravitates toward radicalism and militancy. Writing from a historical perspective, Roman Loimeier sees the Boko Haram phenomenon as consequent to social, political, and generational dynamics within the context of radical Islam. Simon Alozieuwa examines several theories explaining Boko Haram and concludes that each of the theories could offer only glimpses into the whole Boko Haram phenomenon. To him, therefore, Boko Haram is a complex issue that defies a unified theoretical explanation. Ali Bagaji, Moses Etila, Elijah Ogbadu and Ja'faaru Sule interpret the essence of the group as an agenda to impose a religious ideology on a secular community through terrorism. If explaining the purpose and philosophy behind Boko Haram is challenging, it is yet more so because the Nigerian populace filter their explanations through ethnoreligious and political prisms.

Nonetheless, except for a brief analysis by Hussein Solomon, no systematic examination of the responses of the Nigerian people to the activities of the group has been done. For instance, some perceive it as war by Muslims against Christians, some see it as a sponsored conspiracy against the Muslim North, and some as a Northern war against the emergence of President Jonathan, who is from the south-south geopolitical zone. A few regard it as a generic name for criminal gangs in Northern Nigeria. And again, while over-whelming opinions in the south tilt toward scorched-earth approach against the sect, those of the north more likely favour dialogue.

In this research, we examine how Nigerians understand Boko Haram, bandit, herdsmen and how their divergent perspectives exacerbate divisions within Nigerian society. Specifically, this article argues that to an extent the responses to Boko Haram follow divisions within Nigerian society, it follows that the Boko Haram insurgency has succeeded in widening existing cleavages among different groups in the country. Following this introduction, this study looks at the cleavages within the Nigerian state. This is followed by a review of the responses by various groups in Nigeria to Boko Haram, which are framed by Nigeria's prevailing cleavages.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing spread of the nefarious activities of the Boko Haram sect in the Northern parts of Nigeria and the attendant destruction of lives and property is a serious issue that could not be dismissed with a wave of hand. The group caught the attention of international communities following series of violent attacks in Nigeria since July 2009 and the attack of the United Nations building at Abuja in 2011. The sect, having no clear structure or known chain of command was responsible conservatively for the death of over 1000 people. A major function of good government is to guarantee the security of lives and property. This explains why the early philosophers observe that people give up part of their rights to a sovereign leader who is charged with the responsibility of ensuring their security. The demonstrated inability of the Federal Government to curb the insurgence in spite of repeated assurance that all will be well motivates this study.

II. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

- Cattle Rustling and Banditry

The acts of cattle rustling and armed banditry are interwoven in most pastoral communities of Africa. Only on few occasions rustling could take place without involving banditry. This does not dispute the fact

that there have been instances where cattle were quietly stolen in the night or even in the broad day light (Okoli, 2016: 8). In fact, East Africa has high rate of cattle rustling in Africa, drew in the light of this, a protocol of Eastern African Police Chiefs Cooperation (EAPCCO) which legally defined cattle rustling as “the stealing or planning, organizing attempting, aiding or abetting the stealing of livestock by any person from one country or community to another, where the theft is accompanied by dangerous weapons and violence” (EAPCCO, 2008:8). Incidentally, there were a lot of factors that influenced the prevalence of cross- border cattle rustling in West Africa, which include the inability of most states to govern effectively its borderlands, hinterlands and forestlands. (Mohammed, 2016: 10). The study sought to identify and document the root causes, dynamics and implications of the frequent acts of rural banditry and other forms of violence in Northern Nigeria.

Culturally insecurity in the context of herdsmen and farmers relations in Nigeria dates back to when in the first instance Fulani people began to feel insecure in their place of origin and began the search for solutions outside their place of origin. Second insecurity aroused amongst the non-Fulani farming communities when Fulani arrived in their community and engaged in activities that attempts to dislodge the local community. Culturally, Fulani herdsmen are nomad livestock breeders and in pre- colonial times their place of origin was the Sahel and semi-arid areas of Futa-Jalon Mountains in West Africa. But as a result of threat from climatic changes and population growth, made herdsmen to move to the savannah and tropical forest regions of Southern West Africa and far northern Nigeria. Their migration into far Northern Nigeria dates back to the 13th and 14th centuries. And after the Uthman Danfodio jihad they began to integrate with the Hausa and non-Hausa ethnic groups of the middle belt especially during the dry season; and when the number and menace of tsetse flies are reduced in the middle belt of Nigeria. Whereas on one hand crop cultivation and livestock farming are both agricultural activities among local communities for the purpose of providing food and protein for mankind, on the other hand the nomads specialize in livestock breeding particularly cattle breeding without crop production. Consequently, differences in climatic conditions and changes thereof in the North propelled herdsmen to move across regions especially from the North to the Central and Southern Nigeria to access better grazing resources in order to ensure quality food security for their herds. This often takes place during crop cultivation season. While driving cattle across regions sometimes the destruction of crops occur and becomes a source of conflict between farmers who claim customary right over land and herdsmen who are regarded as strangers. By 1978 Nigeria Government introduced the Land Use Act which vests the custody of land in the Federal Capital Territory on the Federal Government/Minister of Federal Capital Territory; custody of Urban Center Land is vested on the State Government and custody of rural area land is vested on Local Government Councils. This is to make it easier for non-indigenes of a particular area to apply and secure land on lease in their host communities as well as provide opportunity for natives to apply and be given a certificate of occupancy to claim ownership of their ancestral lands. Most Fulani who are used to migrating from one place to the other did not take advantage of this. Consequently, they lacked where they could claim as their grazing routes and grazing land. Their increasing movement from one place in the eyes of modern law amounted to trespass and encroachment of the properties of others. Over the years this brought conflicts of interest on land in some places. The Federal Government then identified areas to be known as grazing routes and reserve. This did not solve the problem because there was no compensation as required by law to customary land owners. And herdsmen deliberately stray out of grazing paths into cultivated lands. Nevertheless they coexisted and from time to time traditional rulers come in to adjudicate to ensure that whoever was found guilty paid compensation. But it has come to be noticed that at the time when there were wild animals cattle breeders carried only sticks to defend themselves and their animals. Now that there are no wild animals the cattle breeder carries and uses sophisticated guns

not to attack animals but his innocent fellow human being even in the face of alternative peaceful dispute resolution methods. They have also justified carrying guns to protect themselves and animals against cattle rustlers.

- **Human Security**

The origin of the concept of human security can be traced to the publication of the Human Development Report of 1994, issued by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP 1994). The Report defined the scope of human security to include seven areas:

- Economic security an assured basic income for individuals, usually from productive and remunerative work, or, in the last resort, from some publicly financed safety net.
- Food security ensuring that all people at all times have both physical and economic access to basic food.
-
- Health security guaranteeing a minimum protection from diseases and unhealthy lifestyles.
-
- Environmental security protecting people from the short- and long-term ravages of nature, man-made threats in nature, and deterioration of the natural environment.
- Personal security protecting people from physical violence, whether from the state or external states, from violent individuals and sub-state factors, from domestic abuse, and from predatory adults.
- Community security protecting people from the loss of traditional relationships and values, and from sectarian and ethnic violence.
- Political security ensuring that people live in a society that honors their basic human rights and ensuring the freedom of individuals and groups from government attempts to exercise control over ideas and information.

Unlike many other efforts to redefine security where political scientists played a major role, human security was the handiwork of a group of development economists, such as the late Pakistani economist MahabubulHaq, who conceptualized the UNDP's Human Development Report. They were increasingly dissatisfied with the orthodox notion of development, which viewed it as a function of economic growth. Instead, they proposed a concept of 'human development' which focuses on building human capabilities to confront and overcome poverty, illiteracy, diseases, discrimination, restrictions on political freedom, and the threat of violent conflict: 'Individual freedoms and rights matter a great deal, but people are restricted in what 'Human security can be said to have two main aspects. It means, first, safety from such chronic threats as hunger, disease and repression. And second, it means protection from sudden and hurtful disruptions in the patterns of daily life – whether in homes, in jobs or in communities. Such threats can exist at all levels of national income and development.' (UNDP, 1994). Human security is not a concern with weapons. It is a concern with human dignity. In the last analysis, it is a child who did not die, a disease that did not spread, an ethnic tension that did not explode, a dissident who was not silenced, a human spirit that was not crushed' (MahbubulHaq, 1995).

- ***Boko Haram***

It is based on partially-fixed expressions, highly probable word combinations, conventions and patterns of usage. This means 'Western Education is forbidden'. Unlawful (things or act), it could be along legal, ideological and spiritual lines. Residents gave it the name Boko Haram because of its strong opposition to Western education, which it sees as corrupting Muslims. The term "Boko Haram" comes from the Hausa word 'boko' meaning "animist, western or otherwise non-Islamic education" and the Arabic word 'haram' figuratively meaning "sin" (literally, "forbidden").

Among their objectives and beliefs are: seeking the imposition of Sharia in the northern states; beliefs that western or non-Islamic education is a sin; today's banking system is Shylocks and Islam forbids interest in financial transactions; mixing of boys and girls under the same shade is forbidden in Islam; propagation of the theory that men evolved from the family of monkey as well as the sun in the sky is static and forbidden in Islam. According to them, all these are in conflict with the direct words of Allah. Little wonder, the sect normally dresses in similar costumes as the Taliban of Afghanistan or Pakistan, with long sleeve robe, shortened trousers, a turban, long beard, a small coat cover the long sleeve robe, covering the abdomen (like a bullet proof jacket) and a chewing stick.

However, observers of political events in Nigeria have observed that BH is of two factions. One faction is Yusuf's groups who are head-bent on Islamizing the Nigerian state. While the second groups are the criminal gangs who are supposedly agents of the intellectual, political, traditional and religious elites of the North conscripted after presidential elections for regional political agenda. This was attested to by the Governor of Bauchi State, Mallam Isa Yuguda, who stated that BH are of two types, one faction of the sect distorts the true teaching of Islam, while the other faction is a band of criminals who are out to destroy the country for selfish reasons (Omonobi et al, 2011: 1-5). Corroborating the above information, the BH spokesman Qaqa made it crystal clear that they are prepared to go a step further with Nigerian government to ensure that these groups who are using their name for political and criminal purposes are identified and checked (Aganda, 2012:7).

- ***Terrorism***

There are many definitions for the word *terrorism* as there are methods of executing it. However, most definitions of terrorism hinge on three factors: the method (violence), the target (civilian or government) and the purpose (to instill fear and force political or social change). Terrorism is commonly defined as violent acts (or the threat of violent acts) intended to create fear (terror), perpetrated for an economic, religious, political, or ideological goal, and which deliberately target or disregard the safety of non-combatants (e.g., neutral military personnel or civilians). Another common definition sees terrorism as political, ideological or religious violence by non-state actors. The word "terrorism" is politically loaded and emotionally charged, and this greatly compounds the difficulty of providing a precise definition. A study on political terrorism examining over 100 definitions of "terrorism" found 22 separate definitional elements (e.g. Violence, force, fear, threat, and victim-target differentiation), (Schmid and Jongman, 1988), (Record, 2003). In some cases, the same group may be described as "freedom fighters" by its supporters and as "terrorists" by its opponents, a phenomenon giving rise to the cliché, one man's freedom fighter is another man's terrorist. The usage of the term has a controversial history, with individuals such as ANC leader Nelson Mandela at one point also branded a terrorist.

If no single definition of terrorism produces a precise, unambiguous description, we can approach the question by eliminating similar activities that are not terrorism, but that appear to overlap. For the U.S. military, two of such related concepts probably lead to more confusion than others. Guerilla warfare and insurgencies are often assumed to be synonymous with terrorism. One reason for this is that insurgencies and terrorism often have similar goals. However, if we examine insurgency and guerilla

warfare, specific differences emerge. A key difference is that an insurgency is a movement - a political effort with a specific aim. This sets it apart from both guerilla warfare and terrorism, as they are both methods available to pursue the goals of the political movement.

- ***Insurgency***

This is an armed rebellion against a constituted authority (for example, in the case of Nigerian State) when those taking part in the rebellion are not recognized as belligerents: a usually violent attempt to take control of a government, a rebellion or uprising (Roberts and Timothy, 2009). Insurgencies differ in their use of tactics and methods. According to Robert R. Tomes (2004) he spoke of four elements that "typically encompass an insurgency":

- i. Cell-networks that maintain secrecy.
- ii. Terrorism used to foster insecurity among the population and drive them to the insurgents for protection.
- iii. Multifaceted attempts to cultivate support in the general population, often by undermining the new regime.
- iv. Attacks against the government.

- ***Terrorism – Insurgency Dichotomy***

In arguing against the term Global War on Terror, Fukuyama (2003) said the United States was not fighting terrorism generically, as in Chechnya or Palestine. Rather, he said the slogan "war on terror" is directed at "radical Islamism, a movement that makes use of culture for political objectives." He suggested it might be deeper than the ideological conflict of the Cold War, but it should not be confused with Samuel P. Huntington's "clash of civilizations" (Huntington 1996). Addressing Huntington's thesis, Fukuyama stressed that the United States and its allies need to focus on specific radical groups, rather than clash with global Islam.

Fukuyama argued that political means, rather than direct military measures, are the most effective ways to defeat that insurgency (Fukuyama, 2003). David Kilcullen wrote "We must distinguish Al Qaeda and the broader militant movements it symbolizes entities that use terrorism from the tactic of terrorism itself." (Kilcullen, 2004).

Borrowing from this, there may be utility in examining a war not specifically on the tactic of terror, but in coordination among multiple national or regional insurgencies. It may be politically infeasible to refer to a conflict as an "insurgency" rather than by some more charged term, but military analysts, when concepts associated with insurgency fit, should not ignore those ideas in their planning. Additionally, the recommendations can be applied to the strategic campaign, even if it is politically unfeasible to use precise terminology (Canonic, 2004).

The difference is in the intent of the component activities and operations of insurgencies versus terrorism. There is nothing inherent in insurgency that requires the use of terror. While some of the more successful insurgencies and guerrilla campaigns employed terrorism and terror tactics, and some developed into conflicts where terror tactics and terrorism became predominant; there have been others that effectively renounced the use of terrorism. The deliberate choice to use terrorism considers its effectiveness in inspiring further resistance, destroying government efficiency, and mobilizing support. Although there are places where terrorism, insurgency, and criminal behavior all overlap, groups that are exclusively terrorist, or subordinate 'wings' of insurgencies formed to specifically employ terror tactics,

demonstrate clear differences in their objectives and operations. Disagreement on the costs of using terror tactics, or whether terror operations are to be given primacy within the insurgency campaign, have frequently led to the urban guerrilla or terrorist wings of an insurgency splintering off to pursue the revolutionary goal by their own methods.

The ultimate goal of an insurgency is to challenge the existing government for control of all or a portion of its territory, or force political concessions in sharing political power. Insurgencies require the active or tacit support of some portion of the population involved. External support, recognition or approval from other countries or political entities can be useful to insurgents, but is not required. A terror group does not require and rarely has the active support or even the sympathy of a large fraction of the population. While insurgents will frequently describe themselves as ‘insurgents’ or ‘guerilla’, terrorists will not refer to themselves as ‘terrorists’ but describe themselves using military or political terminology (freedom fighters, soldiers, ‘activists’, jihadist etc.). Terrorism relies on public impact, and is therefore conscious of the advantage of avoiding the negative connotations of the term ‘terrorists’ in identifying themselves.

Terrorism does not attempt to challenge government forces directly, but acts to change perceptions as to the effectiveness or legitimacy of the government itself. This is done by ensuring the widest possible knowledge of the acts of terrorist violence among the target audience. Rarely will terrorists attempt to ‘control’ terrain, as it ties them to identifiable locations and reduces their mobility and security. Terrorists as a rule avoid direct confrontations with government forces. An insurgency may have something to gain from a clash with a government combat force, such as proving that they can effectively challenge the military effectiveness of the government. A terrorist group has nothing to gain from such a clash. This is not to say that they do not target military or security forces, but that they will not engage in anything resembling a ‘fair fight’, or even a ‘fight’ at all. Terrorists use methods that neutralize the strengths of conventional forces. Bombings and mortar attacks on civilian targets where military or security personnel spend off-duty time, ambushes of undefended convoys, and assassinations of poorly protected individuals are common tactics.

Insurgency need not require the targeting of non-combatants, although many insurgencies expand the accepted legal definition of combatants to include police and security personnel in addition to the military. Terrorists do not discriminate between combatants and non-combatants, or if they do, they broaden the category of combatants so much as to render it meaningless. Defining all members of a nation or ethnic group, plus citizen of any nation that supports that nation as ‘combatants’ is simply a justification for frightfulness. Deliberate de-humanization and criminalization of the enemy in the terrorists’ mind justifies extreme measures against anyone identified as hostile. Terrorists often expand their groups of acceptable targets, and conduct operations against new targets without any warning or notice of hostilities.

Ultimately, the difference between insurgency and terrorism comes down to the intent of the actor. Insurgency movements can adhere to international norms regarding the law of war in achieving their goals, but terrorists are by definition conducting crimes under both civil and military legal codes. Terrorists routinely claim that were they to adhere to any ‘law of war’ or accept any constraints on the scope of their violence, it would place them at a disadvantage vis-a-vis the establishment. Since the nature of the terrorist mindset is absolutist, their goals are of paramount importance, and any limitations on a terrorist’s means to prosecute the struggle are unacceptable. From the foregoing, it can be seen that the activities and description of the Boko Haram sect overlaps between the concept of terrorism and insurgency. However, it will be safe to describe the sect as an insurgency rather than a terrorist group, as their activities are a means that tie them more to insurgency.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Rural banditry and other forms of conflict have recently come to constitute a subject of great concern in Nigeria. Studies and other media reports indicate that, in the first quarter of 2014 alone, more than 262 persons lost their lives in 15 separate attacks in Benue state; and subsequent sporadic clashes has continued. In one instance, bandits brazenly attacked the state Governors convoy. Similarly, 16 separate attacks were reported in plateau and Kaduna states in the same period. They led to the loss of 139 lives, with scores of people injured. Zamfara state seems to be the epicenter of rural banditry in northern region. In early April 2015, over 120 people were massacred in YAR GALADIMA village, Zamfara state, by bandits who have, for at least the ten years, been terrorizing rural communities, as well as highway commuters.

The situation in many parts of Nigeria resembles broader Sahel region governance voids. Ungoverned spaces provide a power vacuum, which is at times filled by religious extremist groups and/or criminal elements; they have taken over remote areas where state presence is reduced or non-existent (Aning, 2009). The point made by Mohammed Bello Tukur, Secretary of Myetti Allah Cattle Breeders Association of Nigeria (MACBAN), supports the thesis that weak state capacity to regulate and establish effective governance accounts for the high level of illegal activities perpetrated by criminal gangs and networks. With specific reference to the BirninGwari area of Kaduna State where cattle rustling and related criminal activities have been concentrated, Tukur says,

Almost all the entire herds around that area have been stolen. In fact, that belt; the belt from Birnin Gwari, through Funtua, Faskari, parts of Zamfara going to Anchau that is like a no man's land, for cattle rustlers and bandits. Every cow there has been stolen including cows belonging to general and top civil servants; talk less of small herdsmen whose names you don't hear, Tukur (2013; P45).

They have been people on highway, rustling cattle, looting, laying siege on rural markets and killing innocent people. In June 2018, gunmen attacked and killed 48 people in KIZARA village of Tsafe Local Government Area of Zamfara state. The neighboring state of Sokoto, Kebbi and kaduna have not been immune to these attacks either. For example, a March 2014 attack on Angwan Sakwai of Kaura LGA, Kaduna state led to the death of 57 people with several others injured. In the northeastern states of Adamawa, Bauchi, Bornu, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe, as well as in the remaining central states of Kogi, Kwara and Nasarawa, there have been regular reports of banditry and violence. Actually, in 2013, a local militia ambushed and killed 46 police officers in the village of Alakyoin Nasarawa state. Some other reports also indicate occurrences of such attacks in plateau, Benue, Niger and Abuja in the north central states, Centre for Democracy and Development (2015; P2).

Perhaps no set of factors are implicated in the phenomenon of rural banditry more than the impact of environmental/ecological changes and the declining capacity of the state to maintain security. In addressing ecology and environment issues, it is important to emphasize a number of salient features that have constituted both push and pull factors for transhumance migration across the country, a movement that has often been seen as a catalyst to conflicts and other forms of banditry. This is hardly surprising, for with over 90% of Nigeria's livestock holding located in the country's northern parts, ecological and other forms of climate change propel migrations from the northern-most, drier region to the middle and southern-most regions, and then back again during the rainy season. This migration has historically taken place largely through two corridors: a northwest corridor running from Niger and Benin Republics through Sokoto, Zamfara, Bornu, Katsina, Niger and Kwara states, terminating in Southwestern Nigeria; a second runs from the North-east beginning from Niger, Chad and Cameroun Republics through Bornu, Yobe, Adamawa, Jigawa, Kano, Plateau and Nasarawa states, terminating in the Niger-Benue Basin. Given the demographic changes, desertification, loss of foliage, expanded food production, drying-up of water points, to mention but a few; the pressure on land and the use of land-related resources becomes a key conflict trigger, Mohammed and Ibrahim (2015; p6).

With respect to the state, the effective control over rural areas is a serious cause for concern, and appears implicated in the recurrence of rural banditry and other forms of social conflicts. For all practical purposes, the state is nonetheless able to impose effective controlling urban areas, however tenuous it may be. Such a policy philosophy that lays the emphasis on urban areas is not new, and has its origins in the way the colonial state imposed its rule across Nigeria and other colonized societies. But, this approach to policing became even more glaring since the late 1970s and early 1980s, with the imposition of neo-liberal economic programmes that sought to roll back the state from the provision of critical social services. Rolling back the state had serious implications, not only in terms of the state's ability to impose control, but also in its capacity to project itself as an institution that has "legitimate monopoly over the means of violence.

The rise in private security organizations, the expansion of vigilante groups, the proliferation of small arms and light weapons (SAWLS), the collapse of informal channels of conflict resolution and of securing communities; all became significant channels for citizens to protect or defend themselves in the face of the state's declining capacity to impose effective control. In effect, various contenders to its power bandits inclusive continuously tested the limits of the state in actions such as cattle rustling and other forms of violence, Centre for Democracy and Development (2015; P4-6).

The incessant bloody clashes between the cattle herders and sedentary farmer communities have come to pose serious human security challenges in northern Nigeria. Between 2010 and 2015, the region lost 6,500 persons, \$14 billion and 62,000 internally displaced in 850 perennial clashes in the North Central region alone, Daily Trust (2017). Given the multi-faceted dimensions and the surrounding narratives, tracking down the perpetrators of the crime and finding solutions to the drivers became politically sensitive. In 2017, the clashes between nomadic herdsmen and local farmers led to at least 549 deaths and displacement of thousands in 14 states, Ameh (2018). The killings had continued unabated with the mass burial of over 70 native farmers that lost their lives through the attacks of herdsmen in Benue State in January 2018. As such, the phenomenon of rural banditry in northern Nigeria has transmogrified "from crisis of nomadism to state crisis" Ibrahim, (2016; P7).

Crime thrives in contexts where there's little deterrence. In most of Nigeria's rural communities, there are many opportunities for criminal activity. For one thing, some of these communities are located in remote areas where there is little or no government presence. More importantly, households are in some cases separated by and interspersed with forest areas. This renders them vulnerable to banditry. This situation is made worse by the absence of effective community policing mechanisms capable of addressing the hinterlands' peculiar security challenges. In effect, the incidence and prevalence of rural banditry in northwest Nigeria raise a fundamental question about the government's ability to govern effectively. The state security machinery has so far failed to tackle the scourge of banditry. This failure stems from a lack of political will and operational challenges.

Essentially, the prevailing socio existential conditions in northwestern Nigeria have complicated the security situation. The rural pastoral sector is not well regulated. Illicit artisanal mining and the proliferation of arms in the region are also veritable factors. Geography plays a role, too. Northern western Nigeria's forestlands are vast, rugged and hazardous. Some of the forests run alongside the diverse porous borderlines on the region's frontiers. Borders are poorly delineated, under-policed and thus not well governed. The consequence of this is an abundance of nefarious activity, often facilitated by criminal syndicates. Rural banditry in northwestern Nigeria also derives impetus from the poorly governed mining and small arms sector. Bandits have been drawn to the region by illicit and artisanal mining in states like Zamfara where bandits have been raiding mining sites for gold and cash.

The federal government has recognized the apparent linkage between rural banditry and illicit mining. It suspended all forms of mining in Zamfara state in early April of 2019. Transhumance the movement of cattle is poorly regulated. This has seen it being infiltrated by criminals, which has led to the

intensification of cattle rustling in the region. In states such as Kaduna, Katsina, Zamfara and Kebbi, there exists clan of livestock bandits who specialize in mass cattle raids. While some of these cattle rustling gangs are affiliated to local and transnational syndicates, a number of them are mercenaries of Boko Haram. A cattle rustling constitutes a valuable source of funding for the terror group.

A number of 'push and pull' factors accounted for movements of nomadic herdsmen. Firstly, drought and desertification in West African Sahelian belt occasioned the search for water and pastures beyond the original environment. Secondly, the exponential rise in cattle rustling in northern Nigeria, especially in the Kamuku forest of Kaduna, Falgore forest of Kano, Dansadau forest in Zamfara, as well as the Davin Rugu forest that stretches through the three states, contributed to migration, International Crisis Group, (2017). Thirdly, the insurgency in the North-East, which feeds on cattle rustling, pursued the herders to move to where they enjoyed lesser risks. Thus, transhumance has helped the pastoralists to survive the climatic crises and maintain cultural affinity, Egwu, (2015). Fourthly, population growth among the crop farmers and the increased demand for the limited land spaces for large-scale crops production pitted the two (sedentary and pastoral) farmers against the other. The clashes were usually precipitated by trespasses or movements of livestock beyond the usual transhumance corridors (where they existed), which expectedly led to destruction of crops on farmlands. The cattle herders, in turn, faced the risk of physical assaults, attacks on their lives and, in extreme cases, thievery and killings of their cattle by farmlands owners who suffered varying degree of losses as a result of massive livestock encroachment, UCHE and IWUAMADI, (2018; P72).

The System Infrastructures

- Mobile System

A mobile device is a handheld or portable device that is made to be both compact and lightweight. New data storage, processing and display technologies have allowed these small devices to do nearly anything that had previously been traditionally done with larger personal computers. These devices use broadband system in carrying out complex activities. A mobile broadband system (MBS) is the infrastructure that provides Internet access to mobile and handheld device users. It is a system used by mobile service providers to deliver high-speed broadband Internet access to remotely connected users.

These networks provide for the clients easy interaction, access to resources, business interactions and information dissemination. It also provides means of transmitting various needs to all the points where solutions are needed and can be provided.

Many mobile device users carry out more complex and ubiquitous information processing and management activities and mobile applications offer increasingly sophisticated methods to capture information, to make use of context information and to interact directly with objects in the real world. On the other hand physical objects are increasingly associated with digital information through the augmentation with visual and wireless markers such as RFID tags.

In this context physical mobile interactions allow users to select virtual information and invoke services through the interaction with objects in the real world. Currently there are several approaches for the provision of applications that take such interactions into account. Most of them are proprietary, designed for a special application area or interaction technique and provide no generic concept for the description of real world services.

- Sensor

Some communication system relies heavily on the links interaction between two interacting devices on an internetwork. In most times sensors are used as medium and sometimes transmitters are also used when

radio communication is integrated. The system signal input is usually reflected or outputted by these mediums for the system application to interpret.

Sensor is a device which provides a usable output in response to a specified measurand. A sensor acquires a physical quantity and converts it into a signal suitable for processing. The signal can be digital or electrical depending on the network. Sensors contain active element called a transducer, figure 1 illustrates small sensors that can be embedded into animals with different sizes even though they have the same capacities.

Fig. 1: Sensors of same capacity but different sizes.

Sensors can acquire the following physical quantities which include Biological, Chemical, Electric, Electromagnetic and Heat/Temperature. Other physical quantities acquirable by sensors include: Magnetic, Mechanical motion (displacement, velocity, acceleration), Optical and Radioactivity.

In this work we are particularly interested in extracting Biological and Mechanical quantities from the sensors in our internetworking space. The stimuli measured in mechanical quantities are Position, Velocity, Acceleration, Force, Strain, Stress, Pressure, and Torque. These quantities vary and their values are actually what the system may need as its input. They are actually needed to provide automation. In the design of the system a cost effective but efficient sensor is recommended so that implementation cost will not inhibit the operation of the system.

- Tracking Circuits (Transmitters)

The tracking circuit of the sensor need to be a circuit that is very compact and consumes almost no power. It should be small enough to be hidden in anything you suspect will be lost or stolen. By using a mercury switch or grasshopper a cattle can be “primed” for the time when it is moved and it can be tracked with the application layer. A grasshopper is a switch that is ready to go off at any time. A piece of plastic is placed between two switch contacts to keep them apart and connected to a thread. When the object is moved, the system is turned ON. System trigger like this would make an ideal detector to track down anything going astray. By attaching it to the cows under surveillance, you can follow its removal (rustle) and maybe turn up quite a few surprises. The **Tracker** transmits a very short burst of carrier which produces a blank spot on the dial - commonly called “silence.” Normally, a lot of background noise called “snow” is picked up by a system network when it is tuned to a frequency between the stations. The change between silence and snow produces a “click” or “mow” and this is the noise produced by the cow emitted about twice a second.

In figure 2, the tracking circuit consists of two building blocks both are oscillators. The first operates at a very low rate (low frequency - about 2Hz) and the other operates at approx 90MHz. The first is a square-wave oscillator with a very short “ON time,” while the other is a sine-wave. The only thing they have in common is a “feedback component,” to create and maintain oscillation. In all other respects they are different.

The first block is a 2-transistor **Pulse generator** and the second is an **RF oscillator**. The whole circuit takes very little average current as it is active for very short bursts. But the current is high during the short bursts of operation and we need to check the current taken during the bursts, to make sure it is as low as possible.

To prevent high current, the Pulse Generator circuit is separated from the RF Oscillator with a 1k resistor. To give the Pulse Generator its own separate "Power Supply" a 22u electrolytic was added. The diagram below shows the separate "Power Supply" for the Pulse Generator. The 22u charges via the 1k resistor and when the Pulse Generator circuit requires its "high current," the 22u delivers the energy. This feature is called Stage Separation or Block Isolation and separates the power requirements of a "building block" from the rest of the circuit. The 1k and 22u electrolytic have been connected exactly like a "delay circuit" but they are not used as a delay feature in this arrangement. The 1k slowly charges (in relative terms) the 22u and the Pulse Circuit draws a high amount of energy from the 22u for a very short period of time. The voltage across the 22u drops slightly and when the Pulse circuit switches "off," the 22u charges to maximum voltage.

Fig. 2: A transmitter circuit for tracking object.

The relative advantage explained about the sensor with the transmitter circuit make it unavoidable for the adaption of this sensor for the purpose of the research. These will make the sensor cheap to use per cow and effective in power to allow it last long before any need for possible replacement.

- **Internetwork Devices**

Internetworking is the practice of connecting a device network with other device networks through the use of gateways that provide a common method of routing information packets between the networks. The resulting system of interconnected networks are called an *internetwork*, or simply an *internet*. The Internet is the largest example of an internetworking and it is based on many underlying hardware technologies, but unified by an internetworking protocol standard, the Internet Protocol Suite, often also referred to as TCP/IP.

Internetworking device or connectivity device are devices used to make physical network connections. They do not make changes to the data or transmission route. Connectivity devices operate at the physical layer of the Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) model. Internetworking devices move data across a network. They may direct data to specific locations within the network and/or convert data into alternative formats. Internetworking devices operate at OSI layers above the physical layer. Understanding the functions of these devices and how they fit within the OSI model will help you learn how networks function.

The internetworking devices needed by the system largely depend on how the circuit is wired. If the electrical characteristics of various networks for the sensor and the mobile device are different, media filter adapter connectors may be attached to the mobile device to make the connections possible. But if the sensor circuit includes an internal network interface card (a printed circuit board) then TCP/IP protocol can simply link the devices. The interface card provides the physical connection and circuitry required to access the mobile network. The shortest way recommended in this work is the use of internal transceivers (the combination *transmitter* and *receiver*) in the circuit. It assists in a quick transmission and reception of signals and connects a mobile device to the network.

- Monitoring Cow!

In the design of our system we illustrate how cows will be monitored by herdsmen using the application designed and deployed in the mobile devices. Herdsmen first implant sensors in the skin of cattle.

Fig. 4: An IoT Anti-Cattle Rustling System Design

Theoretical Framework

A fundamental assessment of the subject of this study, reveals, the quest for self-determination, assertion and livelihoods that lie at the heart of the belligerents. It is believed that these acts are calculated reactions against criminal neglect, marginalization, oppression and environmental degradation as well as economic and socio-political hopelessness, experienced by the peoples in Nigeria. In a single word a general feeling of frustration, by some sections of the society (Afinotan & Ojakerotu, 2009). Therefore, the frustration-aggression theory is the most appropriate theory for framing this study.

Clark McCauley (2009) considers the frustration-aggression theory as the American psychologies most prominent contribution to the understanding of aggression and conflict. Consequently, Johan M.G. van der Dennen (cited in Bandura, 1973)¹⁹ argues that this Frustration-Aggression Theory proves to have an immense impact as it appears to have influenced the current Western thinking on aggression more profoundly than any other single publication. Furthermore, Dennen cited in Bandura (1973), observes, “ the theory tends to provide a justification for behaving aggressively: Being frustrated made me do it” . Apparently, all the above positive characteristics make up the reasons for the deployment of this frustration-aggression theory in this study. Besides that, the core contention of this Frustration-Aggression Theory is that obstructionism or blockage of an actor(s) effort to actualize a goal, triggers the aggressive instinct that stimulates the behavioral urge to aggress against, and injure the source of the obstruction engendering the frustration.

Unfortunately, the victims are members of the society and governments. This is a true picture of the situation with most of these abductors, kidnappers and insurgents. Therefore, in this way, the frustration aggression hypothesis explains why people revolt. It gives an explanation as to the cause of violence. This, points to the fact that Dollard et al (1939) is clear that it is hopelessness and despondency that propel the frustration-dynamics to perform the necessary gymnastics that trigger aggression and violent conflict manifested in kidnapping, insurgency and hostage taking.

Consequently, the Frustration-Aggression Theory attributes conflict to the outcome of frustration triggered by obstructionism, betrayal, interference, negligence, failures, deprivation, discrepancy, or the gap between needs expectation and attainment. The fact that there is an air of deprivation, frustration and despondency in Nigeria, make some of the citizens vulnerable to violence as a reaction against government and poor governance. It is believed that the manifestation of these acts of domestic terrorism are merely crafted protests against criminal neglect, marginalization, oppression and environmental degradation as well as economic and socio-political hopelessness, which in one word, is frustration, in Nigeria. The frustration-aggression is therefore the working theoretical framework for this study.

IV. ORIGIN OF TERRORISM (BOKO HARAM) IN NIGERIA

Historically, the act of terrorism has not just begun in the world. It has been for several years. According to Famuyiwa (2014), over 2,000 years ago, the first known acts of what is now called terrorism was perpetuated by a radical offshoot of the Zealots (a Jewish sect active in Judea during the first century AD). The Zealots opposed the Roman’s empire rule of what is Israel today through a determined campaign which involved assassination. The Zealots carry out their attack in crowded places where there will be many people to witness it. This is done in order to get wide popularity and to instill fear in the mind of the generality of the populace (Hoffman, 2008). At the 1972 Olympic Games in Munich, Germany, Eleven (11) Israel athletics were murdered as a result of terrorist attack. This was one of the most notorious examples of terrorists’ ability to bring their course to world attention. In 1981, religion was used to justify and legitimize terrorist violence in the assassinations of Egypt’s President (Anwar Al Saddat) by Islamic extremist and Israel’s Prime Minister (Yitchak Rabin) by a Jewish militant in 1994. In

1993, Muslim terrorist bombed New York City World Trade Centre and an obscure religion Japanese Sect was behind the 1995 nerve gas attacks on the Tokyo subway (Abolurin, 2011). In 1998, Osama Bin Laden's Al - Qaeda organization carried out simultaneously suicide bombings of the America Embassies in Kenya and Tanzania. In 2000 and 2001 respectively, this same organization carried out a suicide attack on a US Navy warship in the harbor of Aden, Yemen (Adegbamigbe, 2011).

Since the October 1st, 2010 Abuja Bomb blasts, Nigeria has been enmeshed in several internal security crises occasioned by the emergence of an Islamic Fundamentalist sect known as *Boko Haram*. Boko Haram is not the first Islamic fundamentalist sect in Nigeria to adopt violence as a weapon of operation. In the 1970s and 1980s, one Mohammed Marwa that was widely acknowledged as dangerous to peace and stability of the nation formed the sect that was known as *Maitatsine*. He instigated riots in the Nigeria which resulted in the deaths of thousands of people as this explains why some analysts view Boko - Haram as an extension of the Maitatsine riots (Johnson, 2011). "Boko - Haram" was derived from Hausa and Arabic words. "*Boko*" in Hausa means "western education". In Arabic word "Haram" means "sin or sacrilege" (Obinna, (2011). Thus, the terms mean "western education is forbidden" is due to the strong opposition to anything Western, as it is believed by the sect to have corrupting influence on Muslims.

The original name for the sect is *The Group of Al - Sunna for Preaching and Jihad*, as this is the English translation of *Jama'atu – Ahlis – Sunna - Lidda'awati Wal – Jihad* (people committed to the propagation of the Prophet's teaching and Jihad). It was founded as an indigenous Salafist group, turning itself into a Salafist Jihadist group in 2009. The group was founded in 2001 by late Muhammad Yusuf in the town of Maiduguri. The residents of Maiduguri adopted the term "Boko - Haram" for the sect. It is an Islamist movement which strongly opposes man – made laws. The organization is a Muslim sect that seeks to abolish the secular system of government and establish Sharia law in the country. The members of the group do not interact with the local Muslim population and have carried out assassinations on any one who criticizes it, including Muslim clerics.

In 2004, Yusuf relocated to his home state, Yobe and settled in the village called Kanamma near the Niger border according to Al Jazeera (2009). The group/sect is believed not to be against Christian alone, but supports opposition to the Muslim establishment and the government of Nigeria. The group largely conducted its operations peacefully between 2002 and 2008. In 2009, the Nigerian government started investigating the activities of the sect. This was on account of security reports that its members embarked on stocking arms and arming themselves as reported in the Guardian Newspaper (2009). Before Yusuf's death, he reiterated that the objective of the sect is to change the current education system and reject democracy. After his death in 2009, his deputy named Abubakar Shekau took over the leadership of the sect. It was believed that the government initially ignored the reports on the sect prior to 2009. Since 2011, with the bombing of United Nations headquarters in Abuja, the sect has been seen by global community as a terrorist group (Alao, et al. 2012). From the historical background of terrorism, it can be observed that terrorism has existed for at least 2,000 years and is likely to remain permanent on political agendas (domestic and international) for years to come, if adequate attention is not promptly taken to curb the menace.

Boko Haram terrorists have in the past claimed responsibility for killing many Muslim and Christian clerics as well as bombing Mosques and Churches killed both Muslims and Christians in some part of Northern Nigeria. Also, they have destroyed many government properties, institutions and displaced or killed so many individuals. One is therefore puzzled as the real motives behind the group's incessant attacks and destruction of both Christian and Muslim places of worship and the killing of its members. Considering therefore the modus operandi of the sect, it may also be asserted that the Boko

Haram may be acting a well written script aimed at destabilizing the Nigeria nation. Though, the terrorist group occasionally claims to be pursuing an Islamic agenda, it may not be incorrect to posit that the group is driven by a sinister political ambition to disunite the country.

This view is corroborated by Apostle Oluyemi, who posited that;

According to Apostle Oluyemi...

“Boko Haram is not a religious organization, and rather it is only using religion to achieve its aim. The terrorist organization is a political organization and its activities have been used to settle political scores. Those people are not Muslims, but classified evil cartel” (Tell Magazine 2011).

It also aptly capture the ideology and philosophy of the Boko Haram sect thus:

“The mission of the sect was to establish an Islamic state where orthodox Islam is practiced. Orthodox Islam according to Mohammed Yusuf, the leader of the sect frowns at western education and working in the civil service, because it is sinful hence for their aims to be achieved, all institutions represented by government including security agencies like Nigeria Army, Police and other uniformed personnel should be crushed” (Tell Magazine, 2011: 12 - 13).

However, some of the specific motives or objectives of the sect as enumerated below include:

- i. Establishment of a fully Islamic state in Nigeria.
- ii. Implementation of a criminal Sharia code (Islamic law) across Nigeria.
- iii. Withdrawal of Northern Muslims from what the sect perceives as non-Islamic government.

To get rid Nigeria off any western influence which include abolition of western education, school for girls and so on.

MODUS OPERANDI: The identified modus operandi of the terrorist group includes:

- i. Suicide bombing.
- ii. Kidnapping of people.
- iii. Use of Improvised Explosive Device (IEDs).
- iv. Sporadic direct gun attacks/shooting at their targets.
- v. Use of fuel - laden motor bikes.
- vi. Use of vehicles laden with Improvised Explosive Devices and so on.

Since 2009 precisely till date, Boko Haram insurgency in the nation has resulted to a several cases of Bomb blasts and thousands of deaths, and many people were injured or maimed for life, properties worth billions of naira have been destroyed and several thousands of people displaced from their abodes (Famuyiwa, 2014). Findings revealed that they have struck and their targets include: Government security agencies (Nigeria Army barracks, Police stations, FRSC, SSS offices, checking points and so on); Government establishments like INEC, United Nations building and people therein; Religion

organizations (Mosques and churches); Educational institutions; Hotels and Beer halls; Media houses and journalists; Community public places like market, football viewing centres, motor parks; Public figures (VIPs) like Emirs, traditional rulers, political aspirants, foreigners (abductions), and gatherings and so on.

For example, the below table shows major attacks of Boko Haram from 2014 till February, 2016:

TABLE 1: MAJOR ATTACKS OF BOKO HARAM FROM 2014 TO FEBRUARY, 2019

S/ N	DATE	NATURE OF ATTACK	STATE	CASUALTY (IES)
1	11/01/2014	Kawuri massacre – Boko Haram attacked Konduga LGA	Borno State	85 people killed.
2	11/02/2014	The Islamic militants (Boko Haram) attacked the local residents of Konduga and it lasted for several hours from the evening with the arrival of gunmen in 4x4 Trucks.	Borno State	A mosque and more than 1,000 homes razed to the ground. 39 people were believed to have been killed and several others injured.
3	14/01/2014	Boko Haram Bombed Maiduguri, killed many	Borno State	31 People killed, 50 injured.
4	16/02/2014	Izghe massacre by Boko Haram terrorists	Unknown	105 People killed
5	20/02/2014	Coordinated attack at Bama	Borno	-
6	24/02/2014	Mass murder of College students as gunmen from the Islamic group Boko Haram shot, burnt and killed students at Federal Government College (Secondary Boarding school) in Buni Yadi	Yobe state	59 People killed (all boys). 24 building in the school including staff quarters were completely razed..
7	27/02/2014	Boko Haram raid village in Borno	Borno State	74 People killed, 54 injured, Over 200 displaced, 34 buildings raised.
8	02/03/2014	Boko Haram bombed Maiduguri, raid village	Borno State	300 People killed, 250 injured, Over 350 displaced, 45 buildings raised.
9	14/04/2014	Two bombs exploded in a crowded bus station in the outskirts of Abuja, Nigeria.	FCT, Abuja.	Over 71 people died and 124 injured.
10	14/04/2014	Bomb attack in Nyaya motor park FCT.	FCT, Abuja.	Unknown
11	15/04/2014	Boko Haram attacked a Government Girl's Secondary School in Chibok and abducted several students.	Borno State.	275 young school girls were abducted.
12	05/05/2014	At night Boko Haram dressed in military uniforms attacked the unprotected town of Gamboru Ngala (a remote town) at the Nigeria – Cameroon boarder; set ablaze houses and shot at the residents indiscriminately whoever tries to escape. Almost all the houses therein were destroyed with IEDs	Borno State.	Over 300 Civilians killed. 17 trucks set ablazed, over 100 vehicles were damaged.

13	02/06/2014	Boko Haram fully kitted in military fatigue uniform attacked the Christian villagers in 3 communities in Gwoza LGA (Danjara, Agapalwa and Antagara). They pretended as military and came with about 10 Hilux vehicles as if they wanted to come and protect them from further attack. They gather a sizeable number of the villagers and opened fire on them all. They also laid ambush for them and used motorcycles to pursue whoever tries to escape. They slaughtered some men; they only freed the young children and women.	Borno State	Over 300 villagers were reportedly killed. 1,000s were displaced. Many churches were razed.
14	23/06/2014	Kano bombing, dozens of people were killed in a bomb blast at Kano state school of Hygiene. The blast was attributed to militant group (BokoHaram).	Kano State	Dozens of people were killed.
15	27/07/2014	Suicide bomb attack on convoy of General Muhammed Buhari in Kaduna	Kaduna State	Unknown
16	30/07/2014	Attack on a Mosque in Yobe	Yobe	Unknown
17	02/11/2014	A suspected Boko Haram suicide bomber targeted a religious procession of the Shia Islamic brotherhood in Potiskum town near Fadiya Islamic school. He pretended to be part of the assembly, but suddenly detonated the explosive vest he wore.	Yobe State	29 people killed and 80 people injured.
18	03/11/2014	Another jail break in Koton Karfe prison in Kogi attacked by unknown gunmen (suspected Boko Haram terrorists)	Kogi State	145 inmates (26 convicted and 119 Awaiting Trials) were freed.
19	3-7/01/2015	Heavy attack with Mass killing, spree killing, petrol bombing at Baga. The targets were the local residents and Nigeria army base in town. Attack attempted by the Islamic terrorists (Boko Haram)	Borno State	At least 150 people fair dead and over 2,000 uncounted for.
20	25/01/2015	Attack of JTF in Maiduguri	Borno	Unknown
21	28/03/2015	Attack on Dukku town	Gombe	Unknown
22	01/04/2015	Attack on Mubi town	Adamawa	Unknown
23	22/06/2015	Bomb attack on a mosque	Borno	Unknown
24	26/07/2015	Bomb attack on Damaturu market	Yobe	Unknown
25	12/01/2016	Attack at Baga	Borno	Over 2,000 people killed
26	29/01/2016	2 bomb blasts rocked a grain market in Adamawa	Adamawa	Unknown
27	30/01/2016	Attack on Dalori and Walori villages near Miaduguri	Borno	Many people were killed
28	04/02/2017	Attack in Damboa town	Borno	2 people killed
29	05/02/2018	Attack in Yobe	Yobe	An SSS man killed
30	07/02/2019	Attack at Kano market and military barracks	Kano	Unknown

Source: Authors' compilation from Nigeria Dailies, Online and others

Figure 1: Hypothetical Organizational Structure of Boko Haram

Source: Onuoha, 2013

Causes of Kidnapping, Banditry, Hostage Taking And Insurgency In Nigeria

- Unemployment

The high rate of youth unemployment in Nigeria is one of the fundamental causes of kidnapping, banditry and other crimes. Most of the industries responsible for the employment of large number of youths are comatose and out of production due to the present harsh economic conditions. Agriculture, which is the highest employer of labour, is also not spared because many farmers have deserted their farms because of herdsmen incursions and attendant insecurity (Ladan and Ladan, 2011). The rate of unemployment may further increase because of the level and spread of insecurity caused by activities of kidnapers and bandits.

- High Rate of Illiteracy

The rate of illiteracy is high in Nigeria (Amzat, 2011). Many children and youths do not go to school, because they simply do not see the need to do so. This is fallout of the poor social values entrenched in the system. This is also a consequence of the unemployment of educated youths. Youths therefore, wrongfully do not see the need to go to school because of the unemployment of graduate youths. The few that are out of school are idle without jobs, and those who are in school cannot go to school because of the problems with our educational system.

All of these compound the poor level of education and literacy in the country. It is evident that most of the bandits and kidnapers are people with little or no education (Akpambor, 2017). This category of people is easily lured into crime because of frustration and inability to assess the risks and consequences of crimes.

- Societal Values

The desire to acquire quick and illegal wealth and the compromised disposition of society on ill-gotten wealth are contributory factors. Our societal values have degenerated from honesty and hard work to quick wealth acquisition syndrome. People no longer question the source of wealth, but are quick to acknowledge sudden wealth without evaluating the means to it.

According to Okoli and Okpaleke (2004) banditry, hostage taking, cattle rustling among others that occur in some parts of the country, are motivated by the desire to acquire wealth illegally, propelled by poor societal values.

- **High Rate of Drug Abuse**

According to the Nigeria Drug Use Survey (2018), there are over 14.4% of the population between 15-64yrs have used either an illicit drug or consumed a pharmaceutical drug for non-pharmaceutical purposes. Thus drug use prevalence in Nigeria is among the highest globally. Ikwuagwu, et. al., (1993) observes the worrisome preponderance of drug use and involvement of young persons in crime. Several studies have established a correlation between drug use and crime. The effects of drug use by individuals form the basis for its cumulative effects on society, especially crime. The effects of drug abuse are felt in the unpleasant criminal activities that are wide spread in the country.

- **Porous Borders**

The land borders are quite porous and not adequately policed or protected. The porous nature of our borders, make it easy for cross border bandits to move into the country, commit crime and move out at will. According to Yahaya, et. al., (2018)¹⁶, the widespread availability of small and light weapons in Nigeria, has its genesis from illegally imported weapons that mostly passed through porous borders that are located in neighboring countries.

- **Handicapped Security Agencies**

It is common knowledge, that we have limited security presence in most states of the federation. It is also obvious that the security personnel such as the police, army, civil defense corps are all not well equipped in terms of manpower and equipment for fighting crime at all levels. This handicap makes it impossible for the security agencies to combat crime resourcefully and effectively. The fact remains that the country's population has increased progressively over the years, without a commensurate increase in manpower of the security agencies. The consequence of the paucity of security personnel and equipment make it practically impossible for the security personnel to control and curb crime. This is further reinforced by non-provision and inadequacy of critical equipment and logistics for security agencies, which are serious constraints.

Consequences of Banditry, Kidnapping and Hostage Taking

The consequences of security infractions on a nation and its citizens are numerous;

- **Loss of Revenue**

Many international communities have designated Nigeria a high risk zone for kidnapping and other violent crimes. Such declarations affect the flow of foreign direct investment (FDI) into the country. This is also affecting the corporate reputation of the country, while at the time affecting tourism. Ejiofor (2015) observes that Nigeria is fast becoming a volatile territory and fast becoming dangerous for investment. The high cases of insecurity suggest that much revenue has been lost overtime.

- **Proliferation of Light Arms and Weapons**

Banditry, kidnapping and hostage taking have contributed to the spread and illegal acquisition of light arms and weapons. This category of weapons are the instruments of trade for the bandits. Suffice to state,

that they need these weapons to be able to carry-on with their business. Therefore, these criminals go out of their ways to acquire these weapons illegally. The types of weapons recovered from bandits, kidnappers and book-haram insurgents are phenomenal, sophisticated and frightening. It is only an indicating of the calibre of illegal arms in circulation in Nigeria.

The most dangerous dimension is that these weapons are now in the hands of indoctrinated children who are being used for dastardly acts. That bandits and kidnappers have access to and indeed make use of military grade weapons and kits to carry out their illegal activities is a worrisome development.

- **Loss of Human Life, Values and Property**

The horrific waste of human life and wanton destruction of property across Nigeria as a result of banditry, kidnapping and insurgency cannot be overemphasized. According to Human Rights Watch Report (2020), insurgents, bandits and kidnappers have conducted numerous attacks on government and civilian targets, resulting in thousands of death, internal displacement of more than two million persons and external displacement of an estimated 243,875 Nigerian refugees. The amount of property destroyed in the past decade over these forms of violent crimes is worth billions of Naira.

Implication of Boko Haram insurgency on Nigeria foreign policy

Following the attempt by Two US lawmakers, Peter King and Patrick Meehan, in April 2012 that Boko Haram should be labeled a terrorist group due to its growing threat, scholars argued that Nigeria would be regarded as “a terrorist state and another axis of the devil.” as the international community will perceived that the country could no longer checkmate the sect. Nigerians will be subjected to more inhuman treatment overseas and every Nigerian will be a ‘suspect’. This will in the long run discourage foreign investment because the country’s credibility before the international community will be seriously questioned. The skyrocketing effect will be felt at international airports and on foreign trade. The spate of insecurity built the worrisome trend, which will massively affect the image of the country.

History shows that violence in Africa rarely raises eyebrows in the West, but the increasing influence of radical Islam in Nigeria has the international community on edge. One point of particular concern is a UN report indicating Boko Haram’s ties with al Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM). The report outlines the arrest of seven Boko Haram members traveling through Niger to Mali in possession of known al Qaeda member’s contact information. Though it’s clear that any coordination between Boko Haram may have with AQIM is advancing day by day, communication between the terror groups certainly spells trouble for Africa and may help explain the increase in violence, the terror franchise has a vested interest in seeing Nigeria fail as a state and becoming a terror safe-haven à la Shabaab in Somalia. From there, Nigeria’s geographic position would make all of North Africa susceptible to Islamic insurgencies itching to battle ill-equipped governments.

Nigeria started 2014 ready to celebrate becoming Africa's largest economy, albeit by updating (rebasng) the standard measure of economic size, GDP. Unfortunately, the festivities were short-lived. In the ensuing months, the rapidly escalating Boko Haram insurgency exposed to all the country's many weaknesses and deep dysfunction that had been partially obscured in recent years by surging oil revenues. While seemingly separate events, the announcement of Nigeria's newly acquired economic status and the stepped-up insurgency are intimately related. In as much as the former is a good news for the country to negotiate diplomatic activities in a position of strength, the latter has deemed the celebration of Nigeria been the largest economy in Africa as such the country is still back to square one in it foreign policy relations.

The increasingly audacious Boko Haram insurgents have been proving too strong for the country's military and other security personnel to handle. For instance, while Nigerian forces were engaged in a fierce battle to recapture Damboa town, which was captured by the insurgents in August 2014, some media reports said the insurgents have also overrun Gwoza community and reportedly slaughtered many civilians while the whereabouts of the emir remains unknown. In the modern world's largely morality-free international politics and hypocritical diplomacy, hopeful and ambitious countries exploit whatever resources, potentials or advantages they have, be it economic, political, geographical, demographical etc., to pursue their interests and achieve their strategic goals. This does not spell anything good for Nigeria in the international community as countries who may well want to assist Nigeria to fight the insurgent may well be doing it to promote its interest. This is seen in the involvement of the United States plan to assist Nigeria to rescue kidnapped Chibok Girls ending in a fiasco as the intelligence gathering assistance they later pledged to provide has turned out to be much below expectation, having probably realized that the crisis does not pose any serious threat to their economic and other strategic interests in the country and the West African sub-region, at least for now and perhaps for the foreseeable future. This explains the apparent failure of the purported intelligence assistance they are ostensibly giving to Nigeria in its struggle to contain the crisis.

Nigeria typically supplies almost half of the Sahel's cereal needs. As a result of the conflict in the north, production is down and prices have spiked causing serious food security concerns in the Sahel, particularly import-dependent, Niger. Isolation, furthermore, undercuts developmental prospects. This is poignantly seen in the global campaign to eradicate polio. Northern Nigeria is one of three locations in the world today where the polio virus persists (Pakistan and Afghanistan being the others). Inaccessibility to the northern region as well as misinformation regarding the purpose of vaccination campaigns risk derailing the latest drive to eradicate the disease – and free up billions of dollars in resources for other public health initiatives around the world.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has offered significant step towards operationalising the way in which the concept of terrorism has been analysed and understood, contrary to George Fletcher's argument that the concept of terrorism is indefinable (Fletcher, 2006). Though, previous studies by Jeffrey Simon (1994), Schmid and Jongman (1998) and Jeffrey Record (2003) has revealed that there was no consensus among scholars on the acceptable definition of terrorism, as there are more than 212 different definitions of terrorism in use (in government circle and other institutions) throughout the world. Yet the definition of terrorism used in this study is significant because it helps to operationalise terrorism in a workable way that can achieve desirable results both in policy and practice.

By developing class theory of terrorism on the basis of the study of Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria vis-a-vis historical method, this study has shown that the discursive frame of terrorism cannot be analyzed and understood in isolation of its class nature and the socio-economic conditions that gave rise to it. In this sense, it was observed that terrorism is an inevitable consequence that will feature more prominently in the capitalist mode of production because the social contradiction (socio-economic crisis) that arises out of the conflicts between the social relations and productive forces will usher a continuous struggle within classes as Karl Marx's Historical Materialism affirmed. Consequently, this perspective locates the present root cause of all forms of terrorism (individual and state terrorism) at the behest of the antagonistic class struggle inherent in global capitalist system. Therefore, state terrorism emerged as a result of the triumphant of capitalism over feudalism, and was sustained through the unending dynamics of capitalist social formation. Like in Nigerian case, the emergence of state terrorism stems from the forceful incorporation of world capitalist system through colonialism, and sustained through capitalist accumulation and capitalist class formation. This study has revealed that state terrorism is in large part, the historical product of class antagonism between the ruling class and other classes in the society. While

individual terrorism was and still generated by the very same historical process that sustained state terrorism: the development of capitalism.

Cattle breeders have also gotten theirs, fear share of this insecurity. I suppose that's why the erstwhile Commandant General of NSCDC Gana was approached based on continuous issue between the breeders the Rustlers and the farmers that sure led to the emergence of Agro Rangers in NSCDC to present rapid responds to such issues on agricultural related and this according to records the incumbent Commandant General Ahmed Audi PhD is substantiating by empowering the relevant units, nevertheless more still needs to be done in this regards by deploying advance technologies.

NSCDC Agro Rangers Rapid Response Squad.
Deployed by the CG NSCDC Ahmed Audi, PhD

The study therefore believes that the problem of insecurity in Nigeria deserves urgent government attention and makes the following recommendations;

- i. The current efforts of various state governments at securing their territories with regional security outfits are welcome. However, state governments should collaborate with all stakeholders at all levels to sufficiently address the situation.
- ii. More security personnel should be recruited at all levels. Particularly for the Nigeria Police and Civil Defense Corps.
- iii. More equipment and logistics should be provided for the security agencies.
- iv. Community Policing system should be effectively and promptly adopted. We have done enough paper work on it.
- v. Democracy and good governance should be encouraged and practiced at all levels. Government and governance should be more accountable, based on justice, equality and fairness and the ability to stabilize politics.
- vi. Government should have the political will and capability to empower the people by creating avenues that will increase their participation in the economic activities of the country.
- vii. Sociopolitical and economic restructuring, the state police, and the creation of more states with a bias towards ethnic minorities are some of the major national issues that would reduce insecurity and separatist agitation.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi .A. (1991). *Leading Issues in Economic Development and Social Welfare*. Kano: Samarib Publisher.
- Abdullahi A.A et al. (2005). *Combating Political Violence in Nigeria: Issues, Prospects and Problems*. Ilorin: Hamson Printing Communication.
- Aborisade., Olademeji., and Mundt Robert (eds). (1990). *Politics in Nigeria*. New York: Longman Publisher.
- Akpambor, N.S. (2017) 'Kidnapping in Nigeria: An Exploratory Study'. *Journal of Social Science* 24(1), 33-42
- Akinola Adeoye, (2011) "Niger Delta Militants and the Future of Nigerian Federalism," *Journal of Social Policy and National Productivity* 1, no. 1: 1–11.
- Afolabi, M.A. (2006). *Inter-group Relations in the 20th Century Nigeria A Histrocial Survey*. Ibadan: Abok Publishers.
- Abonyi, C.J. (2006). "The Impact are the September 11, Attack on the World Politics Journal are International Current Affairs, Vol. 2, N0. 1.
- Ejeh, P.C. (2010). *History and Philosophy of Science*. Enugu: Computer Edge Publishers.
- Ejiorfor, B. A. (2015) *Security and the Nigerian state*. *Japanese Journal of Political Science* 232(1):31-40.
- Imam, Y.O. (2004). *Religious Crisis and Social Disruption in Northern Nigeria*. Ibadan: Loud Books Publishers.
- Ladan S. I (2019). *Banditry and Kidnapping in Katsina State and the Way Out*. Report of a Round Table Interactive Discussion held at the 10th Katsina Forum Organized by Pleasant Library and Books Club Katsina held on 14th April, 2019
- McCauley, Clark and Sophia Moskalenko. 2008. "Mechanisms of Political Radicalization: Pathways Toward Terrorism." *Terrorism and Political Violence*. 20: 415-433
- Mohammed, I.Z. (2002). *The Concept of Economic Growth and Development*. Kano: Samarib Publishers.
- McCauley, Clark. (2009). "Terrorism Research and Public Policy: An Overview." *Journal of Terrorism and Political Violence*. 3: 126-144.
- Okoli, A.C and Okpaleke, F (2014). *Banditry and Crisis of public safety in Nigeria: Issues in national security strategies*. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(4), pp.350-362.
- Odo, O.M. (1999). *Guide to Research Proposal Writing in Social and Behavioural Science*. Enugu: Snaap Press Limited.
- Ojukwu, C.C. (2009). *Terrorism, Foreign Policy and Human Right Concern in Nigeria*. Abakaliki: Willyrose Publishing Company.
- Osuala, E.C. (2005). *Introduction to Research Methodology*. Enugu: AFP First Publisher Limited.
- Shehu, Sani. (2007). *The Killing Fields „Religious Violence in Northern Nigeria“*. Ibadan: Spectrum Book Limited.
- Taro Yammani. (1964). *Statistic: An Introductory Analysis*. (3rd Edition). New York: Harper and Row Publishing Limited.

Boko Haram: Joint Security Task Force Created Deploying. (2011, June 17). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Boko Haram: Thorns of Flesh of the Nation “Damaturu Attack”. (2011, November 11). News Watch Magazine, p. 2

Boko Haram: How it all started. (2011, June 17). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Clement, Idoko. (2012, March 24). FG Seeks Fresh Dialogue with Boko Haram. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Declaration of State of Emergency. (2012, January 16). Broad Street Journal, p. 41.

Declaration of State of Emergency as Part of Government Effort. (2011, December 31). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Desert, Herald. (2011, December 31). As President Security Chiefs and Stakeholders Meet over Abuja Bombing. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Dialogue, The Only Solution. (2012, January 23). News Watch Magazine. p. 40 FG Approves Establishment of 400 Almajiri Schools. (2012, May 9). Leadership. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

FG Sends more Troops to Maiduguri. (2012, April 4). NBF News. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Free Speech. (2011, June 30). Boko Haram: Joint Security Task Force Takes Over Security in Maiduguri. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Halima, C.C (2011, November 11). Meaning of Boko Haram. News Watch Magazine, p.4

Jonathan Lunches School for Almajiri in Sokoto. (2012, April 13). Daily Sun. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Nigeria Declares State of Emergency in Northern Regions. (2011, December 31). Telegraph. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Photo. The Commissioning of the Almajiri Institution in Sokoto State. (2012, April 13). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Promoting the Education of the Almajiri. The Jonathan Recipe. (2012, April 17). News Agency of Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Samuel, Okocha. (2011, December 31). Jonathan Declares State of Emergency in Parts of Nigeria’s North. Digital Journal. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Shehu, Sani. (2011, March 13). Boko Haram: History, Ideas and Revolt. News Diary. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Uduma, Kalu. (2012, January 26). We will Dialogue with Boko Haram – Jonathan. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Nigeria’s Taliban“ enigma. (2009). BBC News. Retrieved July 28, 2009 from <http://www.bbc.com>

Who are Nigeria’s Boko Haram Islamists? (2011). BBC News. Retrieved August 26, 2011 from <http://www.bbc.com>

Boko Haram: Joint Security Task Force Created Deploying. (2011, June 17). Vanguard. Retrieved from

<http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Boko Haram: Thorns of Flesh of the Nation “Damaturu Attack”. (2011, November 11). News Watch Magazine, p. 2

Boko Haram: How it all started. (2011, June 17). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Clement, Idoko. (2012, March 24). FG Seeks Fresh Dialogue with Boko Haram. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Declaration of State of Emergency. (2012, January 16). Broad Street Journal, p. 41.

Declaration of State of Emergency as Part of Government Effort. (2011, December 31). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Desert, Herald. (2011, December 31). As President Security Chiefs and Stakeholders Meet over Abuja Bombing. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Dialogue, The Only Solution. (2012, January 23). News Watch Magazine. p. 40 FG Approves Establishment of 400 Almajiri Schools. (2012, May 9). Leadership. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

FG Sends more Troops to Maiduguri. (2012, April 4). NBF News. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Free Speech. (2011, June 30). Boko Haram: Joint Security Task Force Takes Over Security in Maiduguri. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Halima, C.C (2011, November 11). Meaning of Boko Haram. News Watch Magazine, p.4

Jonathan Lunches School for Almajiri in Sokoto. (2012, April 13). Daily Sun. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Nigeria Declares State of Emergency in Northern Regions. (2011, December 31). Telegraph. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Photo. The Commissioning of the Almajiri Institution in Sokoto State. (2012, April 13). Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Promoting the Education of the Almajiri. The Jonathan Recipe. (2012, April 17). News Agency of Nigeria. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Samuel, Okocha. (2011, December 31). Jonathan Declares State of Emergency in Parts of Nigeria’s North. Digital Journal. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Shehu, Sani. (2011, March 13). Boko Haram: History, Ideas and Revolt. News Diary. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

Uduma, Kalu. (2012, January 26). We will Dialogue with Boko Haram – Jonathan. Retrieved from <http://www.nigeriamasterweb.com>

WEBSITES

Nigeria’s Taliban enigma. (2009). BBC News. Retrieved July 28, 2009 from <http://www.bbc.com>

Who are Nigeria’s Boko Haram Islamists? (2011). BBC News. Retrieved August 26, 2011 from <http://www.bbc.com>